

Pronoun Drop as Evidence of Proficiency: Using Corpus Linguistics to Study Subject Pronoun Expression in Learners of Spanish

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Subject pronoun expression (SPE) in Spanish has been widely researched, specifically in contrast to SPE in non-pro-drop languages. English-speaking learners of Spanish tend to prefer overt subject pronouns over null subject pronouns due to cross-linguistic transfer. Examining SPE in L2 Spanish helps us understand learners' acquisition of conjugations and their awareness of the syntactic structures. Despite extensive research on SPE across Spanish dialects and bilingual communities, there seems to be a gap regarding non-heritage learners of Spanish, specifically in the K-12 context. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the use of overt and null subject pronouns by L2 Spanish learners in dual language immersion schools.

We contrast samples from the Corpus of Utah Dual Language Immersion (CUDLI, 2019): CUDLI is a multilingual corpus of second language writing that contains responses to the presentational writing portion of the Assessment of Performance toward Proficiency in Languages (AAPPL) test. The Spanish subcorpus that we use contains more than 80,000 files by over 21,000 students, and it allows us to compare the production of students with similar instruction across different levels. We will analyze texts from grades 4th to 9th.

This study investigates the morphological features of verbs associated with students' pronoun drop, to determine if there are relevant patterns of influence. Grammatical number and person, among others, have been pointed out as habitual constraints in SPE, as well as lexical frequency, at least in Spanish L1 users (Erker & Guy, 2012). Thus, a statistical analysis would complement our findings about the dual-language-immersion students' acquisition of this feature of the Spanish language.

The findings of this research could contribute to improve language teaching and learning. We want to provide evidence for teachers to improve students' understanding of verbs and pronouns in pro-drop languages. These data could also add to the creation of pedagogic materials.

References

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